

Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons. Part VI. A New Synthesis of 4-Methyl-1,2-benzanthracene

S. M. Mukherji, S. N. Sawhney, and K. S. Sharma

A new synthesis of 4-methyl-1,2-benzanthracene through the Colonge-Mukherji cyclialkylation of naphthalene with 2-allylcyclohexanone is described.

Mukherji and Bhattacharyya¹ obtained 5-(β -naphthyl)hexan-2-one by aluminium chloride-catalysed alkylation of naphthalene with allylacetone. The ketone was then converted to 1,4-dimethylphenanthrene by the sequence of reduction and sulphuric acid-catalysed cyclialkylation, followed by dehydrogenation. Contrary to our expectation of obtaining 1-methyl-3,4-benzphenanthrene by the same sequence of reactions, starting from naphthalene and 2-allylcyclohexanone, we found instead 4-methyl-1,2-benzanthracene to be the sole product, showing linear cyclialkylation, reminiscent of the linear cyclodehydration of 2-(2'- β -naphthylethyl)cyclohexanone, reported by Djerassi *et al.*²

2-(2'- β -Naphthylpropyl)cyclohexanone (I) was obtained in 28% yield by alkylation of naphthalene with 2-allylcyclohexanone under the conditions prescribed by Mukherji and Bhattacharyya¹. The β -orientation of the ketone (I) is based on analogy with the established β -orientation of the product of alkylation of naphthalene with allylacetone and ethyl allylacetate under the same operating conditions. The ketone (I) was reduced by aluminium isopropylate in isopropanol and the resulting alcohol (II) cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid¹. The cyclised product (III) was then dehydrogenated with 30% palladised charcoal to furnish 4-methyl-1,2-benzanthracene (IV), mixed m.p. of which with an authentic sample³, coupled with its UV and IR spectra, confirmed its structure.

1. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, **17**, 1202.

2. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 393; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 2474.

3. Mukherji *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 897.

The linear cyclisation in the case of compound (II) is obviously due to steric hindrance involving the *peri*-hydrogen², so much as to overcome the greater nucleophilicity of the α -position of the naphthalene moiety. 4-Methyl-1,2-benzanthracene was earlier prepared, among others, by Mukherji *et al.*³ through a similar sequence of reactions involving alkylation of tetralin with 2-allylcyclohexanone. The exclusive linear cyclialkylation of the tetralin derivatives³ has also been attributed to the steric factors involved. It is, however, suggested that linear cyclialkylation of the tetralin derivatives is governed by the relatively high nucleophilicity of the 3-position, as evidenced by the facile cyclisation of γ -(5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-naphthyl)butyric acid with sulphuric acid⁴ and the acid chloride of γ -(5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-naphthyl) valeric acid with AlCl_3 to the corresponding anthracene derivatives in excellent yields.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(2'- β -Naphthylpropyl)cyclohexanone (I).—Naphthalene (13 g.) was subjected to anhydrous aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction with 2-allylcyclohexanone (13.5 g.) in dry CS_2 (60 ml) in presence of finely powdered anhydrous AlCl_3 (27 g.) under the conditions described by Mukherji and Bhattacharyya¹. After removal of the solvent, the residual viscous liquid distilled at $220^\circ/2$ mm, yield 7.5 g. (28%). (Found: C, 85.24; H, 7.82. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ requires C, 85.70; H, 8.27%).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 110° . (Found: N, 12.58. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{23}\text{ON}_3$ requires N, 12.9%).

The DNP, prepared in the usual manner, was crystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol, m.p. 107° . (Found: N, 12.14. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 12.50%).

2-(2'- β -Naphthylpropyl)cyclohexanol (II).—The ketone (I) (4 g.) in isopropanol (35 ml) was reduced with aluminium isopropoxide, prepared from aluminium (2 g.), isopropanol (35 ml), HgCl_2 (0.1 g.), and CCl_4 (0.2 ml) in the usual manner. The product obtained distilled at $180^\circ/1$ mm as a light yellow viscous oil, yield 3 g. (75%). (Found: C, 84.63; H, 8.62. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$ requires C, 85.00; H, 8.90%).

4-Methyl-1,2-benzanthracene (IV): 4-Methyl-1,2,3,4,1',2',3',4'-octahydro-1,2-benzanthracene (III).—The alcohol (II) (2 g.) was cyclised by treating it with H_2SO_4 (2 ml, *d* 1.84) at 0.5° for 2 hr. After treatment with water, the product was extracted with ether, washed with 5% NaHCO_3 solution, dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 , and the solvent removed.

The residue (III) (1.5 g.) was dehydrogenated with 30% Pd-C (0.15 g.) by heating at $300-20^\circ$ for 5 hr. The product was extracted with ether and the solvent removed. A light yellow-coloured solid, thus obtained, was crystallised from benzene-ethanol, m.p. $123-24^\circ$; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample³, $122-23^\circ$; yield 1.1 g. (75%) (lit.³ m.p. 123°). (Found: C, 93.88; H, 5.46. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}$: C, 94.20; H, 5.80%).

*Melting and boiling points are uncorrected.

4. Krullpfeiffer and Schafer, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 620.

U. V. absorption: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 227 m μ (log ϵ , 4.7), 256 m μ (log ϵ , 4.8), 266 m μ (log ϵ , 4.83), 276 m μ (log ϵ , 5.03), 286 m μ (log ϵ , 4.96), 323 m μ (log ϵ , 4.3). I.R. absorption: 2860, 1470, 1340, 890, 755 cm^{-1} .

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from ethanol in reddish brown needles, m.p. 146° (lit.³ m.p. 148-49°). (Found: N, 8.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$: N, 8.92%).

The authors are indebted to Dr. Sukh Dev of the National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, for the spectral data.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
THE UNIVERSITY,
KUBUKSHETRA,
PUNJAB.

Received September 5, 1964.